

THE IMPORTANCE OF EPIDEMIOLOGICAL PROCESSES IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS

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Abstract. *The transmission of certain diseases from animals, as well as the fact that the disease can be transmitted when communicating with the patient, and its causative agent enters the body in different ways — through the mouth, nose and genitals, was known as early as that time. Attempts to scientifically substantiate infectious diseases were expressed in the works of Hippocrates, Rosary, ibn Sina and others in the Middle Ages. In his work "the laws of the Tib", Abu Ali ibn Sina expressed thoughts about the main causes that cause diseases, the factors that provoke them, the symptoms of the disease and their prevention. In this article, opinions and reflections on the importance of epidemiological processes in emergency situations will be discussed.*

Keywords: *epidemiological process, Emergency, significance, infectious disease, danger, spread.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОЦЕССОВ В ЧРЕЗВЫЧАЙНЫХ СИТУАЦИЯХ

Аннотация. *О передаче некоторых болезней от животных, а также о том, что болезнь может передаваться при общении с больным, а ее возбудитель попадает в организм разными путями — через рот, нос и половые органы, было известно еще в то время. Попытки научно обосновать инфекционные заболевания были выражены в трудах Гиппократа, Розария, Ибн Сины и др. в Средние века. В своем труде «Законы Тиба» Абу Али ибн Сина высказал мысли об основных причинах, вызывающих болезни, факторах, их провоцирующих, симптомах болезней и их предупреждении. В этой статье будут обсуждаться мнения и размышления о значении эпидемиологических процессов в чрезвычайных ситуациях.*

Ключевые слова: *эпидемиологический процесс, чрезвычайная ситуация, значение, инфекционное заболевание, опасность, распространение.*

INTRODUCTION

It contains information about the invisible pathogens of several dangerous infectious diseases (cholera, plague, chin smallpox, tuberculosis, etc.) and their mechanism, as well as the fact that external factors such as contaminated water, air play an important role in the occurrence of infectious diseases. Ar-Ruzi has described the diseases of Chin smallpox, pertussis. In his works, he was one of the first to think about vaccinating healthy people with a bone taken from a smallpox blister of patients in order to prevent true smallpox. At present, a new direction has arisen — the epidemiology of non-infectious diseases, which studies the occurrence, spread and loss of epidemic diseases. Its main task is to analyze data on the etiology and pathogenesis of such diseases (anthrax, tularemia, leptospirosis, etc.). it consists in developing preventive methods against them, as well as reducing the incidence of deaths among the population from malignant tumor diseases, chronic non-infectious diseases. There are Departments of

Epidemiology at the Tashkent Medical Academy, as well as at all existing medical institutes in Uzbekistan, The Tashkent Institute for advanced training of doctors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Recently, the epidemic situation has interested few people, even in those seasons when it is very relevant. Infectious diseases spread very quickly in autumn, winter and even spring. Here it is important not only to rely on doctors, but also to take independent measures to prevent the spread of viruses. Thus, the organization of anti-epidemic measures falls on the shoulders of many people. Everyone should remember that the prevalence of various diseases may depend on his actions. Anti-epidemic measures primarily include sanitary and hygienic measures. This is a very important component, since it forms the basis of people's health, as well as a basis that reduces people's susceptibility to diseases. Of course, this does not guarantee the complete disappearance of infectious diseases. But subject to hygiene standards, a person's chances of getting sick are significantly reduced. These measures include the study by specialists of such areas of human life as working conditions, nature labor activity, life, physical development, occupational disease. Sanitary and anti-epidemic measures are among the main factors in the fight against the spread of infections.

Of course, if a person is sick, it is better to sit at home and be treated by everyone. Possible methods so as not to cause serious complications. However, there are cases when this is not possible, people need to work in a sick state or move around the city. In this case, it is mandatory to apply a mask so that others do not suffer from the virus. It is worth thinking about this, because not only healthy adults can be infected, but also children, pregnant women, the elderly, for whom the infection can be really dangerous. Now in pharmacies you can find a huge variety of masks, it is better to choose multi-layered models. In this case, the likelihood of infection with the virus is minimal. When accidents, disasters and natural disasters occur, the sanitary and epidemiological situation in the area is significantly complicated. This is due to the following reasons:

1. Destruction of residential and public buildings;
2. Water, sewerage and treatment facilities, municipal and industrial enterprises;
3. Intensive migration of various human contingents;
4. Changes in people's susceptibility to infections;
5. Failure of sanitary and epidemiological and medical institutions located in the disaster zone;
6. presence large number of bodies of people and animals;
7. Mass reproduction of rodents, the appearance of epizootias among them and the activation of natural foci of zoonotic infections.

RESULTS

All of the above reasons significantly worsen the state of sanitation and significantly exacerbate the epidemic situation for many infectious diseases. Therefore, sanitary and hygienic and anti-epidemic measures are one of the components of the national system of Disaster Medicine, an important link in the medical provision of the population and the elimination of the consequences of emergency situations. Sanitary and anti-epidemic provision in emergency situations includes a set of organizational, legal, medical, hygienic and anti-epidemic measures aimed at preventing and eliminating the occurrence of infectious diseases, maintaining the health of the population and maintaining its working capacity. In the process of eliminating the medical

and sanitary consequences of emergency situations, the sanitary and epidemiological provision of the population is carried out:

1. Sanitary and hygienic measures;
2. Anti-epidemic measures;
3. Environmental Control.

DISCUSSION

In order to determine the exact sanitary and hygienic and anti-epidemic measures, it is necessary to take into account the features of various types of factors and consequences of disasters, natural disasters and emergencies the impact of the entire complex on the nature of the sanitary and epidemic situation and the dynamics of the epidemic process in one or another nosological form of The solution to these problems is of great importance and is imposed on territorial centers of State Sanitary and epidemiological supervision and institutions of the sanitary and epidemiological service. Sanitary and hygienic and anti-epidemic measures are one of the most important activities of authorities, health and other services in emergency situations, both in everyday life and in times of peace and war. They are goals aimed at solving the following issues:

1. Maintaining and strengthening the health of the population, prevention of diseases;
2. Incident warning infectious diseases among the population;
3. Their rapid elimination in the event of the occurrence of infectious diseases.

Sanitary and hygienic measures-a set of measures carried out in order to preserve the health of the population and participants in the elimination of the consequences of emergency situations in the emergency zone. The main ones are:

1. medical control of the state of Health;
2. Sanitary control of living conditions;
3. Sanitary control of food and water supply;
4. Sanitary control of bathroom and laundry services;

In the area of emergency situations, the following sanitary and hygienic measures:

1. Organization and conduct and determination of the assessment of the sanitary and hygienic state of the territory harmful factors impact on the health of the population and the environment;
2. Organization and participation in the organization and sanitary control of the living conditions of the population in the emergency zone, its food, water supply, bath and laundry services;
3. Organization of the personal composition of emergency facilities, participants in the elimination of the consequences of the accident, as well as sanitary and hygienic measures to protect the population;
4. organization sanitary control at objects of hygienic importance that ensure the vital activity of the population in the territory of emergency situations;
5. Structures and institutions participating in the elimination of the consequences of emergency situations are responsible for ensuring the state of health of the personnel, their provision with special clothing and protective equipment, medical control over their correct use;
6. Participation in the control of the sanitary condition of the territory, its timely cleaning, disinfection and burial of dead and dead people and animals;

7. Organizational and explanatory work on the personal composition of the objects of emergency situations in the emergency zone, on the rules of the regime and behavior for participants and residents in the elimination of the consequences of the accident.

CONCLUSIONS

Case of failure of water supply facilities and networks, measures were established to provide the population with quality water. Anti-epidemic measures in the zone of action and in the regions close to it should be aimed at neutralizing the sources of infection, disrupting the routes and mechanisms of infection with pathogens, increasing the immunity of the population, reducing the likelihood of developing certain forms of infectious diseases. And to reduce the influence of various extreme factors on people. Depending on the climatic and geographical conditions, the season of the year, the type of accident, the accident or the natural disaster among the population, the spread of viral hepatitis, typhoid fever, dysentery and other acute intestinal infections, as well as natural hearth diseases (cholera) can be expected. The possibility of the appearance of other diseases, for the Prevention of which special measures are needed, is not excluded.

REFERENCES

1. Tadjiyev M., Ne'matov I. "Civil protection of emergency situations", Tashkent-2003.
2. Ergashev A., Ergashev T., Ecology, epidemiology. 2005 y.
3. Rustamova, R. P. (2022). THE ROLE OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE INDIVIDUAL. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(NUU Conference 2), 898-903.
4. Parpievna, R. R. (2022). ACTUALITY AND DIRECTIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG STUDENTS. Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences, 2(3), 139-146.
5. Parpievna, R. R., & Zafarovich, O. R. (2021). Application of Artificial Neural Networks for Analysis of Pathologies in Blood Vessels. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 4074-4082.
6. Ravshan, O., Ra'no, R., Usmon, A., Risbek, S., & Azizkhon, K. (2020). The aral tragedy and its threats to regional life, issues of cooperation in solving the aral problem. International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research, 9(4), 3016-3021.
7. Rustamova, R. (2022). TA'LIM MUASSASALARI O'QITUVCHILARINING MEXNAT SHAROITLARI XAVFSIZLIGINI OSHIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 297-301.
8. Abdilkadimovna, K. N. (2022). THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF GENDER RELATED WORDS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE. YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 1(2), 179-182
9. Shodiyeva, G. N. K., & Dustmatov, H. (2022). CLASSIFICATION OF WORDS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH: IN THE EXAMPLE OF VERBS. *Central Asian Academic Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(4), 234-237.
10. qizi Shodieva, G. N., & Dusmatov, H. H. (2022, July). RINCPLES OF DIVISION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 38-43).

11. Karaeva, K., Tukhtaeva, K., Ibragimova, Z., Djuraeva, M., & Saidova, S. (2020). Main peculiarities of teaching efl in mixed-ability groups. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(5), 1712-1715.
12. Tukhtaeva, K. DIVERSE OPINIONS ABOUT MODERN CASE SYSTEM IN THE ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES.
13. Komilova, N. (2022). GENDERED LEXICON OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B4), 192-194.
14. Sotvoldiyevna, U. D. (2022). Political Euphemisms in English and Uzbek Languages (A Comparative Analysis). *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 9, 92-96.
15. Satvoldievna, U. D. (2021). Axiological Characteristics Of English, Uzbek And Russian Phraseological Units. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(06), 40-45.